

STUDY ON MARKETING COST, MARKETING EFFICIENCY OF VEGETABLES BETWEEN ORGANIZED AND UNORGANIZED MARKET IN ANANTAPUR DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH.

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(MS Received: 06.06.2023; MS Revised:17.07.2023; MS Accepted:18.07.2023)

MS 3075

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS)

Abstract:

The present study named Study on Marketing cost, marketing efficiency, of Vegetables between Organized and Unorganized Market in Anantapur district of Andhra Pradesh. This study aims to investigate Marketing cost, and Marketing efficiency of Vegetables between Organized and Unorganized market in Anantapur district of AP. The present study was conducted on year 2021-2023. The study was conducted in Bathalapalle, Atmakur block of Anantapur district. For this study 5 villages were selected from Bathalapalle, Atmakur block, the study reveals there is marketing cost, marketing efficiency in comparatively higher.

Keywords: marketing cost, marketing efficiency, Anantapur, vegetables between Organized and unorganized market

Introduction:

Indian retail the sector is predominantly unorganized. However, organized retail units are fast emerging and becoming the prefer choice of consumers, especially in urban areas. The organized retail sector implies presence of large retailers, greater enforcement of taxation mechanism and better labour law monitoring system. Organized retailing of fresh produce in India took off in the post liberalization era. Due to change in consumer Demographics, the increase in families, income, urbanization, awareness and access of internet media has influenced the consumer behaviour to choose products from modern retail outlets. The success of organized retail format, any format for that matter, significantly depends on consumer's patronage. . Vegetables are one of the most needed and consumed items. Every household consumes vegetables on a daily basis, though some purchase them for 2-3 days because they have the luxury of the refrigerator

Objectives:

1. To work out marketing cost of vegetables in the market
2. To work out marketing efficiency of Vegetables in the market
3. To evaluate Producer share in consumer rupees.

Materials and Methods**Selection of District:**

For the present study Anantapur district was purposively selected, as it has large area under organized and unorganized market.

Selection of Block:

The sample consists of total 18 blocks. Out of these blocks Atmakur and Bathalapalle block were selected purposively by sampling procedure which are having highest organized and Unorganized markets.

A. ATMAKUR

B. BATHALAPALLE

Selection of Villages:

A list of selected two blocks having 23 villages out of these 10% villages was selected randomly for the selected study.

S no	Villages	No of Respondents
1	Apparacheruvu	40
2	Obulapuram	35
3	Cherlopalli	50
4	Goridindla	10
5	Thopudurthi	15

Selection of Respondents:

The respondents for the study considered of consumers belonging to different income group having different occupation from the selected villages were selected. For survey 10% of respondents were selected from each village based on proportionate representation of income to the population size therefore the total of 5 villages and 1 respondents

Data source and Data types

The study used a mixed-methods approach, combining primary and secondary data. Qualitative data was collected through focused group discussions, interviews with RBK, and personal interactions with relevant individuals. Additionally, secondary data was gathered from existing reports, agricultural records, and government websites pertaining to Anantapur district. Information was also obtained through personal interviews.

Methods of data analysis:**Marketing Cost:**

The total cost, incurred on marketing either in cash or in kind by the producer seller and by the various intermediates involved in

the sale and purchase of the commodity reaches the ultimate consumer

$$\text{Marketing cost} = C - C_f + C_{m1} + C_{m2} + C_{m3} + \dots + C_{mn}$$

Where:

C = total cost of marketing

C_f= cost born by the producer from the time produce leaves the farm till the sale of produce.C_{mn} = cost incurred by middlemen in the process of buying and selling.**Marketing Efficiency:**

Where Market efficiency refers to the degree to which market prices reflect all available_relevant information if markets are efficient, then all information is already incorporated_into prices.

$$\text{MME} = \frac{FP}{MC + MM}$$

Where

MME is modified measure of marketing efficiency

FP= Price received by farmers

MC= Marketing cost

MM= Marketing margin

Results and Discussion:**Table 2: Marketing Cost of vegetables between organized and unorganized market**

Particulars	Vegetables	
	Number of responses	Percentage Distribution
From who commission agent purchased		
Farmer	40	26.6%

Trader	30	20 %
Commission Agent	30	20 %
Cold Storage	40	26.6 %
Total	160	100.00
From who retailer purchased		
Commission Agent	150	100.00
To whom commission Agent sold		
Retailer - Trader	95	63.3 %
Commission Agent	5	3.3 %
Total	100	100.00
To whom Farmer sold		
Commission Agent	40	100
To whom retailer sold		
Retailer	10	6.6 %
Consumer	140	93.3 %
Total	150	100.00

Table 2 shows that sourcing pattern of vegetables through organized and unorganized market. It reveals that for vegetables 40 percent of the commission agents purchases are made directly from farmers, whereas about 30 percent from traders, and 26 percent from cold

storage points. Thus, contact with farmer is significant but not very large. On the other side mainly, the commission agents sells to retailers and retailers sells directly to the consumers except for some retailer to retailer sale

Table 3: Marketing efficiency of vegetables between organized and unorganized market

Particulars	Channel I		Channel II	
	Amount	Percent	Amount	Percent
Price received by the farmer	202.63	25.08	214.77	33.04
Cost incurred	82.68	10.23	83.43	12.84
Contractor's purchase price	285.31	35.31	0	0
Cost incurred	33.70	4.17	0	0
Margin	100	12.38	0	0
CA/Wholesaler's purchase price	419.01	51.86	298.20	45.88
Cost incurred	37.71	4.67	22.66	3.49
Margin	60.00	7.43	55.00	8.46
Retailer's purchase price	516.72	63.95	375.86	57.82
Cost incurred	38.57	4.77	38.57	5.93
Margin	252.71	31.28	235.57	36.24

From the above table marketing efficiency shows that price received by the farmer 33 percent, and the cost incurred by the receiver is 12

percent, and the wholesalers purchase price is 45 percent having the total amount with marketing efficiency through channels.

Table 3: Producer's share in consumer rupees of Vegetables between organized and unorganized market:

s.no	Vegetables	Apparacheruvu	Obulapuram	Cherlopalli	Goridindla	Thopudurthi
1	Tomato	31.9	46.7	29.3	38.6	45.5
2	Cabbage	28.2	40.0	29.0	34.6	46.2
3	Carrot	54.1	60.0	72.7	70.6	72.5
4	Capsicum	53.3	41.2	47.4	69.0	57.1
	Average	43.4	47.5	46.4	53.3	57.7

Conclusion:

Survey finds that consumers purchasing vegetables in supermarkets and Vegetables stores account for the higher proportion: they are 68.91% and 55.77%, respectively. Therefore, more enterprise brand Vegetables should be put in supermarkets and Vegetables stores. In addition, with the rise of the network Table 10: Binary logistic analysis of the factors influencing the behavior of purchasing

enterprise brand Vegetables. B Journal of Food Quality 7 economy, the convenience of online shopping is highlighted. 36.54% of consumers purchase Vegetables in online stores. So giving full play to the role of the internet, establishing online stores through e-commerce platforms is one of the important ways to sell enterprise brand Vegetables in the future. Secondly, improve the quality of enterprise brand Vegetables and pay attention to the improvement of

taste. Survey respondents generally believe that there is a difference between enterprise brand vegetables and common vegetables (39.74%). biggest difference lies in quality and safety.

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